

From Orality to Ghostliness: Self-Translating the Haunted Self in African Literature

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Abstract

In this study, I examine the challenges faced by Francophone African literary authors, such as Olympe Bhêly-Quénum, in self-translating the haunted, oral “self” into colonial languages. Like most African literary writers, Olympe Bhêly-Quénum enriches his works with African elements that describe his sociocultural background. These elements are woven throughout his texts as narrative spectrality conveyed by lexical and discursive structures of African orality, tone, songs, etc., which risk being flattened in translation. Throughout his *Le Chant du Lac*, Olympe Bhêly-Quénum uses para texts to self-translate certain hauntings into French while claiming that others remain untranslatable. The current study is set out within the framework of the “Pre-Writing Phase” of translation in African literature to demonstrate how the unspoken indigenous nuances of African languages are (un)translatable. The para texts of Olympe Bhêly-Quénum’s *Le Chant du Lac* and their self-translations serve as the primary data for the present study. I analyse the African ghostly elements and the effects of their translation by mapping their fate across the

translation chain. I argue that the translation of the African text should aim at producing decolonial, rather than colonial, effects on its readership. By revisiting Jacques Derrida's theory of Hauntology, I conclude the study by proposing a new orientation strategy for (re)presenting African spectrality across cultures.

Keywords: Translation, Haunting, Africa, Literature, Text, decolonial